

DURABILITY OF SODA-LIME-SILICATE GLASSES. PART V. EFFECT OF ULTRAVIOLET RADIATIONS ON CHEMICAL DURABILITY

BY H. N. DAS GUPTA AND AMALENDRA NATH CHOWDHURY

Effect of long and short waves of ultraviolet rays on durability of chilled glass has been studied and the chemical durability of glass in bulk is attended with some definite increase as a result of the effect with a decrease in the surface resistivity.

It is well known that long-wave ultraviolet rays penetrate ordinary glass and quartz, while short-wave rays penetrate quartz, but are completely absorbed by ordinary glass. In the present communication the effect of ultraviolet rays of both long and short waves on the chemical durability of chilled glass has been studied. It will be evident from the experimental portion that when unannealed or chilled glass is exposed to these radiations, whether of short or of long wave-lengths, there is some definite increase in the chemical durability of glass in bulk. The surface resistivity, however, is found to decrease, indicating thereby an increased surface alkalinity. In this respect the effect has been found to be analogous to that of annealing (cf. Williams and Weyl, *Glass Ind.*, 1945, 26, 275, 325; Sen, Chowdhury and Das Gupta, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 379). The chemical resistivity of glass is expressed as the solubility of alkali and, as such, the determination of durability of glass was made by taking recourse to "power test" (Faraday, *Phil. Trans.*, 1830, p. 49; Pelouze, *Compt. rend.*, 1856, 43, 117; Mylius and Foerster, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1092; *Z. Instrum.*, 1889, 9, 120; Hagmaier, *Mit. Chem. Eng.*, 1917, 16, 604; Nicolardot, *Compt. rend.*, 1919, 169, 335; Peddle, *J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1920, 4, 3, 299; 1921, 5, 72, 195).

In Part IV of the present series (Chowdhury and Das Gupta, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 425) it has been observed that soda-lime-silicate glass, whether chilled or annealed, when subjected successively to powder test after intervals of 24 hours each, gives residual sulphuric acid values (R. S. A. V.) of descending magnitude and up to a restricted number of times. Similar R. S. A. Vs. are also obtainable with glass exposed to ultraviolet radiations (Table VII).

A prospecting set for fluorescent minerals, designed by Fraser and Chalmers (*Trans. Inst. Min. Met.*, Vol. LIV, 1944-45), was used as a source of short-wave ultraviolet rays. From this set about 25% of the total input energy is emitted as radiation, the distribution of which is approximately as shown in Table III. For longer waves ultraviolet lamp was used. The analysis of the radiation from such a lamp is given in Table IV.

Four different specimens of glass were exposed to ultraviolet radiations. Three such specimens of different compositions were prepared in the laboratory, while the other sample, blown in the form of a bottle, was procured from a firm at Howrah. This was not allowed to anneal. The effect of longer exposure on durability of glass could not, however, be studied owing to restriction in respect of continuous running of the appliances for the ultraviolet radiations.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Three new glasses of different compositions were melted and plained in the usual way, in separate Morgan crucibles. Each was withdrawn, while white hot, from the furnace and was cooled rapidly. Lumps of moderate thickness were used for different exposures. Table I gives the purity of the ingredients used, and Table II shows the percentage batch composition.

TABLE I

Material.	SiO ₂ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	MgO.	Na ₂ O.	Loss.
Sand ...	97.3%	0.31%	1.6%	0.39%	Trace	...	0.29%
Lime ...	1.85	0.75	2.68	70.99	Trace	...	23.8
Soda ash ...	0.29	...	...	S. trace	S. trace	48.76%	16.2

TABLE II

Batch No.	SiO ₂ .	CaO.	Na ₂ O.
A	74%	11.5%	14.5%
B	74	10	16
C	68	10	22

TABLE III

Distribution of U. V. radiation from the prospecting set.

Type of radiation.	Distribution of radiation (output)					
Short-wave U. V. (2537 Å)	...	...	...	...	...	60%
Long-wave U. V. (3132 and 3650 Å)	...	...	...	...	...	10
Visible light	...	...	...	...	...	25
Near infra-red	...	...	...	...	...	5
						Total 100

TABLE IV

Analysis of radiation from the lamp.

Wave-length.	Rel. comp. of the U. V. radiation.	Wave-length.	Rel. comp. of the U. V. radiation.
4040 Å	2.7%	3340 Å	4.5%
3650	91.0	3130	1.8
			Total 100

For each exposure, lumps weighing approximately 15 g. were taken. The source of radiation was practically in contact with the glass lump in every case. Powder test was made in the usual way after exposing the sample for 1 or 1½ hour. Exposure for shorter period was avoided as this did not give comparative results. In order to test

the effect of radiation on surface durability of glass, lumps were powdered to pass 150 mesh to increase the total surface area. This powder was then exposed to radiations. The results of "powder test" obtained after exposure to short-wave radiation have been incorporated in Table V and those of long-wave in Table VI.

TABLE V

Sulphuric acid value after exposure to short-wave U. V. radiation.

Specimen.	S. A. V. of chilled sample.	Form in which exposed.	Duration of exposure.	S. A. V. after exposure.
Howrah glass	2125.4	Powder	1 hour	2222.7
	2130.9			2230.2
B	509.2	Lump	1 "	2032.5
		Powder	1 "	2029.6
	Lump			1 "
		500.0	594.6	
				431.9
				434.1

TABLE VI

Effect of long-wave U. V. radiation.

Specimen.	S. A. V. of chilled sample.	Form in which exposed.	Duration of exposure.	S. A. V. after exposure.
Howrah glass	2125.4	Powder	1 hr.	2197.2
	2130.9			2194.5
A	250.5	Lump	1	2023
		Do	1	2019
	Do			1
		261.4	218.1	
C	1285.1	Lump	1	197.1
				Do
	Powder	1	1184	
			1280.6	1193
				1039.1
				1032.5
				1318.7
				1325.3

It will then be clear from Tables V and VI that the surface durability of glass definitely decreases due to such exposures. Table VII gives the results of residual sulphuric acid values.

TABLE VII

Specimen.	Duration (days).	R. S. A. V.	Specimen.	Duration (days)	R. S. A. V.
Howrah glass	1	1259.5	A	1	62.4
	2	808.7		2	41.3
	3	421.3		3	15.7
	4	270.3		4	Nil
	5	190			

DISCUSSION

No decisive conclusion regarding the effect of ultraviolet radiations on glass could be arrived at, pending collections of further facts. However, a tentative suggestion is put forward.

In a communication Moore (*J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1949, **33**, No. 154, pp. 265-275) has suggested, on theoretical grounds, that the condition in molten alkali-lime-silica glasses will tend towards reduction rather than oxidation. According to him the tendency of reduction to occur is due (a) to thermal instability of many peroxides (and certain oxides) at the temperatures used in melting glasses, and (b) to temporary combination of loosely held oxygen atoms with the alkali ions diffusing through the glass. Evidence, bearing on the above mentioned deduction, has actually been collected by Moore and Prasad (*ibid.*, 1949, **33**, No. 155, pp. 336-70), after investigating spectro-photometrically the colours given by iron in glasses of alkali-lime-silica and alkali-lime borosilicate types.

Accepting the views of Moore, it is to be expected that in a molten glass the alkali metal is largely ionised and, as such, the condition represented by $\equiv\text{Si-O}^-$ and Na^+ must exist, at any rate to a large extent, even if all the alkali atoms are not ionised. The alkali ions diffuse through the glass at rates depending on temperature and it is proposed that the "natural alkalinity" of chilled glass is due to this. When, however, a chilled glass, in bulk, is exposed to the influence of ultraviolet radiations, perhaps strengthening of the bond between the alkali ion and the anionic net-work is brought about. This imparts an increased durability to glass in bulk. The total surface area of the same weight of powdered glass is undoubtedly considerable. At the surface, however, the alkali metals appear to be under two-fold influences, viz., (a) of radiations, and (b) of weathering agent, the effect of one being opposite to that of the other. During exposure appreciable quantity of ozone formation takes place. The ozone perhaps exerts its weathering influence on alkali metal on the surface and offsets the effect of ultraviolet radiations. If this assumption be correct, we should naturally expect decreased durability by such exposures. Further work in this line is in progress.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA

AND
DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY, FUELS AND METALLURGY,
INDIAN SCHOOL OF MINES & APPLIED GEOLOGY,
DHANBAD.

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